

BELMONT
FORUM

PARSEC

AGU
ADVANCING EARTH
AND SPACE SCIENCE

FAPESP
FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA
DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO

International Teams and Data Sharing: A Case Study with 40 Researchers, 6 Countries, and one Data Management Plan

5 October 2022

This work is generously funded through grants from:

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ANR

A Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan (DDOMP) ensures that the data is organized, sharable, and reproducible, and helps researchers gain recognition and credibility through data sharing.

Vocabulary

DDOMP: Contains all of these things...

DMP Data Management Plan
 Digital Object Management Plan
SMP Software Management Plan

Object Any digital research product; managed for the team
Output Final research product; preserved for open access

Data and Digital Output Management Plan

A Step-By-Step User Guide for Building a Successful Data Management Plan

Why is a Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan (DDOMP) important? Ensuring proper data management helps Belmont Forum researchers achieve the goal of supporting international transdisciplinary research to provide knowledge for understanding, mitigation, and adaptation to global environmental change, and is required of all Belmont Forum-funded projects. A DDOMP ensures that the data is organized, sharable, and reproducible, and helps researchers gain recognition and credibility through data sharing.

Awarded Projects

A full Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan for an awarded Belmont Forum project is a **living, actively updated document** that describes the data management life cycle for the data and other digital outputs to be **collected, reused, processed, and/or generated**. As part of making **research data open by default, findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable** (FAIR Data Principles).

Pre-Proposal

[Find Guidelines](#)

Full Proposal

[Find Guidelines](#)

Awarded Projects

[Find Guidelines](#)

Repositories...
FAIR Data...
Preservation...
Rich Metadata...
OK? Got it?

**Data Science
Strand Team Members**

Um...
Not Sure What You
Mean.

**Synthesis Science
Strand Team Members**

PARSEC Project Elements

- No new observational data will be created.
- All team members will comply with the decisions codified in the Data and Digital Output Management Plan (DDOMP)
- All team members signed a Code of Conduct for the project.

Step 1

- Take the robust requirements of the DDMOP and create a workbook and tools making it operational for the PARSEC team members.
- Consider:
 - Decision making for the project and team members that support the needs of the researchers **during the research effort** that complies with the Belmont Forum requirements.
 - Decision making, **preparation, and preservation for digital output of the project** to comply with Belmont Forum requirements.

PARSEC DDOMP Workbook

Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook for the Belmont Forum

Collaborative Research Action (CRA) Science-driven e-Infrastructure Innovation (SEI) for the Enhancement of Transnational, Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Data Use in Environmental Change

Project Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Reuse through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas (PARSEC)

June 2020

Introduction

This Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook (DDOMP) are used by the PARSEC team to establish the policies the team will follow, document the operational procedures necessary to comply with those policies, and the planned activities necessary to manage PARSEC data, software, and other digital outputs. This is a working document.

The Belmont Forum Open Data Policy and Principles state that:

Datasets should be:

- Discoverable through catalogues and search engines
- Accessible as open data by default, and made available with minimum time delay
- Understandable in a way that allows researchers—including those outside the discipline of origin—to use them
- Manageable and protected from loss for future use in sustainable, trustworthy repositories

The FAIR Guiding Principles state that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

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1. The procedure for selecting datasets requiring preservation
2. The procedure of protecting digital objects during the life of the project
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PARSEC - Operational Procedures for selecting datasets for preservation.

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 1.1 Datasets and other digital objects of long-term value are identified, including data type and encoding, 1.2 How the data and other digital objects will be collected, captured, or created.

A fundamental principle of the PARSEC project is to promote data reuse and will NOT create any new earth observation data. All raw data needed for our work already exists and includes household survey datasets and satellite imagery. Datasets significant to our research are logged in our [Dataset Tracking](#) tool as well as any processed or derived dataset.

PARSEC is using existing raw data that includes satellite imagery available at various resolutions, time-series, and costs from instruments associated with our country partners: US, Brazil, France, and Japan. To perform ground truth analysis with our models we are using local household surveys for towns and villages associated with our selected sites. These are sourced primarily from global operations such as the WHO World Health Survey with more precise data available (if needed) from the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), carried out by ORC Macro for the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the Living Standards Measurement Study (LSMS) surveys, conducted with technical assistance

from the World Bank. Depending on the selection of protected area sites, we are likely to need to access additional, already existing, survey data.

Much of this data is available in both detailed and aggregated forms. For the detailed data we must submit formal requests and comply with the terms of use and necessary protections for this sensitive information.

PARSEC output data will include global gridded socio-economic information and socio-economic dynamics specific to our study sites.

Our primary data and digital products planned for preservation include:

- Cleaned observation records and measurements
- Aggregated datasets subjected to quality control protocols, used for machine-learning and artificial intelligence models. This includes the provenance of what data was used to develop the aggregated dataset.
- Documentation of the quality control protocols used
- Algorithms developed to prepare data (cleaning scripts) and perform analyses
- Software supporting machine learning and artificial intelligence models
- Results of our analysis
- Training and workshop material

Dataset Preservation: If a dataset is used for analysis, it is to be preserved and made available prior to the end of the project or if more time is needed then before the final report is submitted to the Belmont Forum. We track this in the table where all datasets are logged. For any papers written during the PARSEC project, datasets used to support that research must be preserved and available at the time of publication.

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How many
pages are in
that DDOMP?

20?

And still being
updated?

Uh. No.

Step 2 - We Need Some Decisions...

Using the DDOMP Workbook:

- PI and team leadership make the decisions about data and software management and preservation for the team. Reference Operational Procedures section for the list of decisions to make.
- Decisions need to account for institutional requirements, funders, and journals. Comply with any law or required protections, and access/control management.
- Update workbook with decisions and make available to team.

Dear PI...

Oh, great one.

Your research has no bounds.

Please accept these **simple guidelines** to help your team manage their data and software as you explore your hypothesis.

Also, please use **your prominent position to ensure the team follows the checklist that you establish.**

Please **share with the team your dedication to robust data and software management** making preservation and publication much simpler when the time comes.

Remember, your funder, journal, and **mother require you to cite your data.**

Also, data citation can lead to an increase in citation for your paper. This is a bonus for promotion and tenure time!

Sincerely,
Your DDOMP Coach

Benefits of a Workbook

Supports the iterative / flexible needs of the research team

Provides guidance on “what data/software”, “where to store”, “what to track”

Provides guidance on when actions are taken

Gives method for

- what to do **during** the project
- how to **preserve** your digital objects for **publication and sharing**

Checklist for your team to make it “super simple”

Validation task for the PI to ensure **compliance** and **consistency**

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Checklist for your team to make it “super simple”

Validation task for the PI to ensure **compliance** and **consistency**

Details to follow

Step 3 - We Need Checklists...

Using the DDOMP Workbook:

- Build checklists for the team to use based on the decisions.

DDOMP Checklist Part 1: Team Resources

- Material development and temporary storage location
- Team communications and information decimation tools
- Dataset storage location during the project
- Software development platform
- Data preservation (including derived products) repository
- Software preservation repository
- Training, workshop material preservation repository

DDOMP Checklist Part 1: Team Resources

- Material development and temporary storage location
 - [Google Drive](#)
- Team communications and information decimation tools
 - [Email, Slack](#)
- Dataset storage location during the project
 - [Open Science Framework \(AWS integration\)](#)
- Software development platform
 - [GitHub](#)
- Data preservation (including derived products) repository
 - [Environmental Data Initiative](#)
- Software preservation repository
 - [Zenodo](#)
- Training, workshop material preservation repository
 - [Zenodo](#)

DDOMP Checklist Part 1: Team Resources

- Material development and temporary storage location
 - Google Drive
- Team communications and information decimation tools
 - Email, Slack
- Dataset storage location during the project
 - Open Science Framework (AWS integration)
- Software development platform
 - GitHub
- Data preservation (including derived products) repository
 - Environmental Data Initiative
- Software preservation repository
 - Zenodo
- Training, workshop material preservation repository
 - Zenodo

PARSEC

- PIs – 4
- Country Leaders – 5
- Funders – 4
- Researchers – 40
- Languages - 4

DDOMP Checklist Part 2 – Tracking and Reporting

Once (during lifetime of researcher)

- **ORCID profile** - activate the automatic updates from Crossref (published papers) and DataCite (published datasets and other digital objects. Reference this page for instructions: http://bit.ly/ORCID_Trust

Weekly

- Track **datasets created**, track **datasets used**, track **workflow/provenance**

Monthly

- Publish and Report **conference presentations and posters**
- Peer-reviewed Papers – and Supporting Digital Objects
 - Deposit and preserve **Datasets**
 - Deposit and preserve **Software**
 - Report **publications with citations to datasets, software, and other digital objects**

Quarterly

- Update your ORCID profile and ensure accurate and complete to ensure proper credit

Step 4 – Trust but Verify...

Using the DDOMP Workbook and Checklist:

- The PI, or designee, validates the team is following the checklist. Very important when establishing new habits.
- Nudge any researcher as needed.
- If this matters to the PI, then it will matter to the team.

Data Stewardship

Software Stewardship

What PI's Need to Know - The Sheepdog Role

As the Principal Investigator (PI), you are responsible for the progress and accomplishments of the entire research team.

In order to comply with the data and software sharing requirements of your funder and publisher you need to incorporate a set of processes and decisions that need to be made as you begin and conduct your research.

Your team needs to support these decisions and help ensure the proper stewardship is being conducted throughout the entire project.

What PI's Need to Know - The Sheepdog Role

Things to do:

- Make decisions on **data and software storage during your project** that best support you as you progress and when you are ready to preserve your datasets and software.
- Make decisions on **data and software preservation** that you will use prior to publishing your research or even during critical milestones.
- **Contact the preservation repositories** to ensure the methods you chose for managing your data and software will make it easier for deposit. This includes not only the format of your data, but information (metadata) to document as you go. You don't want to guess at this later if you forget to capture it.
- Make sure you are **following your institution requirements, as well as your funder(s), country, and your selected publisher**. Also, take into account requirements from researchers you are collaborating with from other organizations or countries.
- If you are collecting data from countries that **require permission** to do so, or even to take the data outside the country, make sure you begin this process early enough to deal with necessary steps.
- And FINALLY, make sure **your team is following the practices you have put into place through tools like checklists**.

Thank you

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